

Journalism in the spaces between: Studying interlopers from an audience perspective

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Abstract:

This paper is part of a larger project utilizing interviews with interloping journalists, analysis of their content, and an interactive audience study to examine journalistic outsiders from new angles. As journalistic outsiders, interlopers offer particularly contrarian approaches to journalistic work, approaches which further inform their relationships with members of the public. Members of the public also recognize the contrarian nature of interlopers, and consider this relationship when negotiating the information value of interloper content. Findings presented here highlight how interactive audience research can help us further understand those who challenge, and at times expand, our understanding of news and journalism by drawing in the perspectives of those who consume it. In its conclusions, this paper advocates examining journalism through the critical interactivity audiences have with interloper content, locating journalism within the spaces where these relationships play out.

Keywords: Interlopers, Audiences, Journalistic Field, News as Knowledge

Introduction: Interlopers as Journalistic Outsiders

Among recurring questions for journalism scholars, some of the most persistent are: ‘what is journalism?’ and its corollary ‘how do we define it?’. Time has shown that it is near-impossible for one paper to resolve the first question definitively, and the second is open to any number of methods and interpretations. With that in mind, this paper focuses on one aspect of what journalism is in a digital age, applying a specific set of approaches to understand journalism through the relationship between journalistic ‘outsiders’ and members of the public who encounter their content. For its object of study, it focuses on digital media outlets that have established reputations for presenting news and information which runs contra the mainstream; a category of media termed interlopers (Eldridge, 2014). These media offer fruitful opportunities to understand the extent to which we can see a journalistic field widening, moving away from ‘core’ notions of the field which dominated in the twentieth century. This paper does so by also moving away from content-centric (discourse and content analyses) and interloper-centric (interviews and surveys) methodologies. It incorporates audience reactions to interloper content as a way to understand the place such media content might have in the journalistic field. As part of a research project titled *Interrogating Antagonists*¹, it aims to better understand the changing boundaries of the journalistic field through new theoretical and methodological approaches.

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In focusing on interlopers, this paper builds on a body of work which has sought to make sense of digital media actors who identify their work as journalism but are not traditionally recognized as such. 'Interloper media' was a specific terminology coined to reflect the way pronounced journalistic outsiders openly challenged the established field of journalism by claiming they too belong (see, among others: Eldridge 2013, 2017, 2018). Originally 'Interloper Media' was adopted in examining tensions between traditional journalists and digital upstarts from WikiLeaks to rudimentary news blogs to larger digital-native outlets. It has since been built upon to address a widening range of actors who contribute to journalism from both inside and outside the traditional field (most explicitly in the work of: Belair-Gagnon & Holton, 2019; Cheruiyot, Baack & Ferrer-Conill, 2019; Holton & Belair-Gagnon, 2018).

This paper circles back to the original definition, examining the work of outsiders who embrace a critique of traditional media while simultaneously positioning their work as news content (see: Eldridge, 2018, pp. 3-5; p. 24). Yet in its approach, it deprioritizes the confrontation between interlopers and other news media (though that remains a feature), and focuses on the ways relationships with publics are formed through the content interlopers produce. This is something which has been overlooked in previous work addressing these media actors, and is a response to the call from Hanusch and Banjac (2019, p. 28), who argue that in an ever-more fragmented field, with new digital actors emerging, "the ways in which the impact of audiences and new journalistic actors need to be taken into account". Finally, this paper considers as well that while some interlopers remain at odds with the field, there have been signals the gap between journalism's more traditional and its more interloping actors may be narrowing (Eldridge, 2019). The choice to focus on interlopers and publics is thus two-fold. First, it draws attention to media pushed to the edges of the journalistic field. Second, by incorporating a focus on the response from members of the public (rather than journalists) it reflects approaches to understanding journalism through its social interaction; it adopts this approach as a way to understand journalism from the 'outside' and work its way 'in'.

Revisiting core/periphery distinctions

Describing the journalistic field in terms of an inside/outside, or core/periphery structure has been utilised in research which focuses on the boundaries of the journalistic field, and how an 'in-group' and 'out-group' dynamic is reflected in reactions to digital newcomers. A number of studies beginning at the turn of the century have identified this 'core/periphery' structure in responses to blogs, citizen journalists, and other digital media. Each has been framed as an unwelcome newcomer and as confronting 'mainstream' journalism – including by flagging their 'interloping nature (Deuze & Witschge, 2017; Lowrey & Gade, 2011; Robinson, 2015; Schudson & Anderson, 2009). Across such work this distinction is identified as part of a power dynamic elevating the established journalistic actor in contrast to the newcomer (Eldridge, 2013).

This reaction is also problematized, seen as an exertion of social power to the detriment of new voices who may *also* invigorate society with new information while embracing journalistic aims (Singer, 2003). Critiques recognize that while these differentiations are to be expected, and in this case are reflective of reactions to newcomers, the boundaries these

reactions construct are based on a set of “collectively shared and taken-for-granted assumptions underlying the belief that journalists, acting in their normative roles, ought to wield gatekeeping control over news content on behalf of society” (Lewis, 2012, p. 845). Nevertheless, the core-periphery metaphor does have its uses. For one, it builds from a well-established sociological perspective on the nature of journalism as a field, one which has some power to exert itself in our modern societies, and one that has been at pushing back against those who would see themselves as new entrants to that field (Bourdieu, 2005). A core-periphery metaphor reflects how fields unite around principles of “vision and division” (separating a core and a periphery) which provides journalists with a sense of coherence about what they do (being part of the inside, not the outside) (Bourdieu, 2005, p. 36).

This vision is not, however, an inherent vision. It is the result of ongoing contestation among those who see themselves as journalists, contestations which emphasize certain aspects of the field, and ‘complicities’ that mask deviations from this vision (Bourdieu, 2005, pp. 35-36). Analytically, when we refer to the core, we point to the best manifestation of these points of emphasis, and those providing the clearest reflection of the dominant vision of the field (Bourdieu, 2005, p. 37; Schultz, 2007). Historically, this has both been shaped by and represented by traditional and dominant legacy media who make visible this picture of what journalism ‘is’ (Benson, 1999, 2006).

But just as this vision is not inherent, the boundaries they inform are also not ‘settled’ and constantly need to be built and rebuilt. Boundary research has shown those in professions and profession-like fields, including journalism, projecting a sense of vision and division in order to expand, expel, and protect their sense of exclusivity, articulating boundaries around what they see as the core definition of the field (Carlson & Lewis, 2020). Boundaries are drawn by emphasizing otherness, such as distinguishing good journalism over bad (Bishop, 1999; Berkowitz, 2000), or information over activism (Tong, 2015), or exclusive claims of journalistic authority (Carlson, 2017, p. 37). For journalism, these boundaries once surrounded a relatively narrow picture of journalism, honed in the twentieth century around a consolidated profession where few had the resources to compete for belonging (Waisbord, 2013). This is no longer the case, and we see the field shaped as well by a weaving together of persistent understandings of journalism from tradition, alongside digital change (Ryfe, 2019).

This offers a starting point to focus on interlopers as pushing back against a core/periphery distinction, challenging the dominant vision of the field, and crossing boundaries which have been constructed to exclude their work. We can see reactions to digital newcomers which push them to the periphery as hesitancy towards change, either for its own sake or for fear that it may weaken the claims of authority journalists make. From the brief discussion above, we can also understand these are not in and of themselves sufficient to explain how interlopers position themselves, or how they are responded to from the public. They are better seen as reflections of the power dynamics at play in defining journalism as a field.

While the aim here is to move us away from prioritizing these boundary-drawing reactions, a final note on the metaphor of a field built around a core is worth establishing. In all the change that journalism has witnessed in a digital age, scholars continue to observe an *idea* of journalism persists, one that retains some purchase in our societies beyond the discussions of what journalism ‘is’ amongst academics and practitioners. Even if it is sometimes hard to

pin down, journalism is *something* in our modern societies, and that *something* still holds some value in people's lives, (Donsbach, 2010, p. 38). It still matters (Schudson, 2018). Those on the periphery, while challenging the nature of boundaries as hegemonic power structures, *also* see there is something of value in this widely-held vision of journalism. They may attack boundaries as performances of institutionalized power and the commercial priorities of news media (Benson, 2006, p. 188), and challenge the taken-for-granted-ness of the field, but they also, in many ways, aspire to have their work appreciated in the same way (Eldridge, 2018, p. 125). Yet, whether for adopting unique approaches to sourcing, to publishing, to writing, or simply embracing new affordances of digital media, they find themselves on the outside looking in.

And in their persistence, interlopers challenge us to think about whether the field, to the extent it is bounded, is problematically narrow. They force us to ask whether defining the field around journalism's traditional core allows tradition to be the defining picture of journalism, one which may not account for the effectiveness of content produced by interlopers. They highlight where boundaries have been constructed to the benefit of those doing the constructing, forcing us to question the taken-for-granted assumptions that journalists' authority is exclusively held. Given the prevalence of alternative and digital sources of news, and information coming at us from new types of interloping journalists, they challenge us to redraw the picture of the field nowadays.

News in a Journalist-Public relationship

It's all well and good to want to deprioritize traditional structures around the field, but there remain some challenges. Among them, how to study interlopers as journalism without predicating the assessment of their work by any traditional or established sense of what journalism 'is'. One avenue for doing so draws from the literature on news as knowledge. This enables a study that looks not only at what the public thinks about interlopers as journalism, but what they come to know from their work.

From Park (1940), we are encouraged to approach news as a form of public knowledge, and journalists a type of knowledge worker. Nielsen (2017) offers us a way to look at knowledge derived from digital news in a revitalization of Park's discussion, one which recognizes that in a particularly crowded digital landscape the knowledge derived from digital content can be fleeting, or it can be more profound. He sees the types of knowledge which people derive from digital news as sitting on a spectrum between an 'acquaintance with' (something informal, intuitive, and unsystematic) on one end, and something more deeply derived, as 'knowledge about', on the other. Nielsen categorizes these in three types of news, pinned to three types of content: "news as impressions, [in] decontextualized snippets of information"; "news-as-items, [in] self-contained, discrete articles"; and "news-as-relations," in content explaining data (2017, p. 93).

In this 'New Chapter' on the sociology of news, Nielsen calls for further work examining news as knowledge. While his discussion focuses on digital types of content from larger news media outlets primarily, in his approach there is an opportunity for understanding journalism from beyond the traditional field as well. First, Nielsen reminds us that when assessing the contributions made by any digital news content towards society, there is an implied interaction between the producers of content engaging in a type of knowledge production

and consumers of content engaging in a type of knowledge acquisition. The same spectrum he indicates might be found if we turn towards the content produced by interlopers to see if members of the public acquire knowledge from news, how they see digital information in terms of how it fulfils specific societal needs, and in both cases to what degree. This reorients our attention from distinctions between digital interlopers and traditional field members towards emphasizing the prevailing social contract between journalists and the public (Ekström, 2002, p. 260), in whatever forms that might now take.

Second, this interaction between journalists, news, and public has been a central tenet to how we have come to understand journalism, and it remains relevant today. This is not something that goes unnoticed by journalists, by news media, or by audience members. Journalists imagine an audience when constructing their content – an imagined public they hope is more-or-less a reflection of their actual audience. News media imagine a public as an audience they hope will consume (including paying for) their content. Members of the public, when consuming news, assume they are more-or-less a part of that journalist's or media's imagined audience, sticking with or abandoning content accordingly (Conboy & Eldridge, 2018).

We have addressed news, and an orientation towards publics, but not publics themselves. In lieu of a repetitive literature review, we can situate the public within a long line of understanding the media role in public formation, from the Lippman v. Dewey debates of the 1920s, to the writing of Anderson (1983) and Habermas (1981, 1989) in the 1980s. Warner's (2002) discussion of publics and counterpublics is a furtherance of these discussions. Warner shows publics can be something broadly constituted (a national public), but more often is assembled narrowly, and assembled by being addressed, in media, through the circulation of texts. In fact, Warner sees a public as a group which can be best understood by exploring how it is assembled in this way: "It exists *by virtue of being addressed*" (Warner, 2002, p. 50). He highlights how the public, much like the field of journalism, can be conceptualized as something that is not inherent, but which is assembled through this circulation of texts. As a process of social construction, when individuals engage with texts, they coalesce as publics by "speaking, writing, and thinking" (2002, p. 52).

In such a line of thinking, there is a specific and prominent role for media. Media allow a public to be assembled, and a public which adopts and circulates messages from media has power in the media-public relationship; each allows the other to be known. From Warner, news provides the 'space' for the discourse which assembles a public. From Nielsen and Ekström we can focus on that space to see how productive it is by examining how informed that public is, and how the relationship between journalists and their public is maintained. This places emphasis back on news, and the reciprocal relationship of knowledge production and acquisition embedded within it.

Drawing this closer to discussions of news as a type of knowledge, we can understand that for each side of this dynamic, the relationships between journalists and publics is constantly being negotiated around what content is useful. That negotiation primarily takes place via the content each engages with. There are rarely sit-downs between journalists and their publics, and even in a social media age the meaningful exchanges between journalists and publics are limited. Instead, the meeting up of publics and journalists takes place now through the way

news travels within a “decentralized informational ecology” (Broersma, 2019, p. 517). Broersma’s emphasis on a decentralized ecology is integral here, as he encourages us to see media content as being elevated to the status of news when it is valued by members of the public, irrespective any official ‘stamp of approval’ that it came from a journalistic source (see also: Swart, Peters & Broersma, 2019). The decentralized ecology he outlines is an invitation to think of news outside stable media-audience relationships, and not to act as if any one of these are enduring – rather, they may be more-or-less ongoing, or more-or-less ephemeral, depending on the nature of audience members and their media repertoires (Hasebrink, 2017).

While attention to the journalist-public relationship builds on a well-established understanding that news is dependent on the reception of content by audiences, when it comes to interlopers this relationship has been glossed over as other definitional criteria are applied, including criteria which emphasize difference over familiarity. Indeed, the relationship between interlopers and their audiences is often dismissed as something irrational, emotional, or based on political fervor. This downplays the perspectives of members of the public who value interloper work, and risks ignoring when interlopers succeed at perform a familiar socio-informative function in a more interactive digital media space. We can therefore examine how interlopers are perceived as more-or-less journalistic by members of the public to broaden our understanding of journalism. This breaks from a dominance of journalist-centric approaches which assess how outsiders’ work is understood among journalists by instead prioritizing the views of their public.

Methodology: Stepping outside

This paper represents only one aspect of the larger *Interrogating Antagonists* project. Which employed interviews, analysis of content and comment threads, and interactive audience research during the Spring and Summer of 2018. It focuses on digital news sites (in the US, UK, and Netherlands) which have attracted broad attention for their alternative approaches to producing fact-based content. The overall study gathered more than three hours of interviews with interlopers, analysis of their sites and content including comment threads, four hours of recorded interactive group research sessions, and approximately 1,240 individual entries in interactive research diaries from 15 participants. This paper focuses on results from the group sessions and participants’ interactive research diaries.

For the audience research, this project began with an array of 21 sites (Table 1). These range from fully digital-native (e.g. *BuzzFeed News*) to now-digital media (e.g. *Vice*); they incorporate a wide political spectrum (e.g. *thecanary.co* on the far-left; *TPO.nl* on the far-right), and a variety of coverage (politics, culture, technology, local, and international content). Critically for this study, this list includes sites which have been the subject of previous research on interloper media, including established but simplistic sites run by one or a few people (e.g. *eschaton*, *DrudgeReport.com*, *Order-Order*), as well as more substantial, digital operations (e.g. *Deadspin*, *Jezebel*). It also includes a number of sites which are not notably antagonistic or upstart in nature, but nevertheless reflect an approach to news and information emerging from outside the traditional field (e.g. *Axios*, *BoingBoing*). It also includes sites which push against lines of decency and acceptability in their approaches to content, while still offering (more or less) fact-based content (e.g. *Geen Stijl*). This allowed the

study to consider different reactions to different types of outsiders when evaluating participants' research diaries

Table 1, Sites studied.

Site Name	Category	Orientation
The Slot*	Politics, US, left	←←
Order Order*	Politics, UK	→→
TPO.nl	News/Politics, NL	→→→
The Canary*	News/Politics, UK	←←←
Axios*	Politics/News, US	±
Jezebel*	News/Culture, US	←←
Sikkom*	Local News, NL	±
Drudge Report	News, Politics, US	→→
Geen Stijl*	News/Culture, NL	?
BoingBoing*	News/Culture, US	←
The Verge*	News/Technology	±
Gizmodo*	News/Culture/Technology, US	←
BuzzFeed News*	News/Culture, US	←
Eschaton	News/Politics, US,	←←
Little Green Footballs*	News/Culture, US	←±
The Young Turks*	News/Politics, US	←
Deadspin	Sports/News, US	←
Feministing*	News/Culture, US	←←
Bellingcat*	News/Geopolitics, UK/EU	←±
Vice*	News/Culture US(Canada)	←
Bustle*	News/Culture, US	←←

* indicates site used in interactive research
 ←, ±, → indicate political leaning and degree.

The audience study had 15 research participants (8 women, 5 men, 2 non-binary), between 18 and 33 years old, from 8 different countries. All had at least a secondary-level education. Participants were introduced to the project in a 2-hour orientation session where they visited and compared traditional and peripheral news sites and recorded reflections on: first impressions, stories they read, whether or not they would return to one on their own, how they judged content, presentation, etc. Each participant was then given a 'menu' of three most-different digital news sites (e.g. one left-leaning cultural, one-right leaning political, one local) to check twice daily for two weeks. Consideration was given when participants identified sites they would not be comfortable checking frequently (e.g. *TPO.nl*, a far-right site based in the Netherlands). In the end, 17 sites (starred in Table 1) were used for research diaries, with each site having at least three participants.

Research diaries were compiled using individual closed, encrypted, anonymized WhatsApp group chats (one per participant). Participants recorded their perceptions of sites along the same lines as the orienting research session. Feedback was encouraged in any form, (entries included drawings, screenshots, longer written feedback, the use of emoji, audio recordings, and short snippets in the form of conversational texting). Participants could also offer perspectives on other news and media they encountered, but had to at least relate these to

their 'menu'. The researcher also monitored the 17 sites daily. This allowed the research to capture participants' assessment of news content as it was published, rather than from a pre-selected sample of content, and allowed participants to engage with news in their everyday routines (submitting feedback while waiting for a train, over breakfast, while bored at work). Participants were also encouraged to ask technical and clarifying questions.

By using mobile messaging apps, interaction could be incorporated in ways standard diaries would not allow.² In addition to participants registering their comments via WhatsApp, the researcher posed occasional broad questions to participants (e.g. 'what stood out on your sites today?'; and, 'Did you click on any links that took you outside your sites?'), or prompt the participants to recall specific topics of coverage from the period of study. Questions and prompts avoided being 'on the nose', so nothing addressed how 'journalistic' they felt the sites were, or the 'degrees of knowledge' they were able to derive from sites. The same prompts and questions were delivered to all participants.

A final in-person session was held to discuss themes which surfaced while monitoring the diaries, and to clarify any points. Participants were paid €50 for fully participating, with partial compensation for partial participation. A research assistant transcribed all interviews, research sessions, and WhatsApp diaries, which were transcribed, anonymized, and archived.³ Personal data was kept separate from any digital or archived record. Any data, including diary entries, from participants who dropped out partway through the study was removed from the study.

Participants' research diaries and the group discussions allow this research to address several research themes in understanding interlopers from a public perspective:

Theme 1: The (perceived) public for interloper/outsider content: Is it a broad public, or a fragmented narrow public? Is it an 'insider' audience, an oppositional one? Is the content something which *should* be made public?

Theme 2: The content published on interloper and outsider sites: Is it useful? Is it informative? Is it a distraction, diversion from 'real' news? Does it contribute something to the audience for their daily lives?

Theme 3: The relationship between interloper sites and other types of news: Do outsiders fill a news void? Or, rather, are they a portal to other sites? Are they trusted, or does one need to 'check' their stories?

Findings I: Overview

One of the first clear findings is that, even for a digitally adept set of participants who said they engaged actively with digital media including news, this study broached new terrain.

² It is worth noting the ability to interact with the researcher was mentioned as something that helped them stay invested in the study for the full two weeks.

³ My thanks to Nathalie Fridzema, who served as research assistant on this project, for transcribing interviews and recorded sessions, organizing the group research sessions, and facilitating those sessions.

When asked during the first activity of the group research session to navigate to any site of their choosing for news, all but one of the participants chose a major newspaper or public broadcaster's website. This reinforces the need for orientation within these types of studies. Once introduced to the sites above, participants were able to apply the same considerations to new types of content that led to them to visit traditional news media. Few participants had pre-existing familiarity with any of the sites (and when they did, these were: *Jezebel*, *BuzzFeed News*, *The Young Turks*, and *Sikkom*, a Groningen-based news site). With some exceptions – identified below in the discussion of Quadrant IV – orientation was quickly achieved (within 2-3 days participants were no longer 'making sense' of their sites).

In their evaluations of both traditional and interloper sites in the first session, participants demonstrated flexibility when encountering new types of informative content from interlopers. This is not to say they saw them equally. Expectations for what news *should* do still came to bear, including both normative and personal expectations. This is reflected in this response from Participant 1: "Yeah, it is not really 'news news' *per se*, but a kind of news"[P1]. In some cases, the preference for more 'familiar' content remained a reference point in research diaries, as did normative assessments around objectivity, balance, and tone (regarding sarcasm, inappropriate language, sensationalism). This was both a point of critique – seeing outsider content as not 'news' for these reasons [P4; P20] – and a point of praise when openly subjective content was seen as a transparent approach, and a positive take on news [P1; P21]. For most participants traditional media stopped being mentioned as the main criterion for evaluations once they gained experience with the content they were following (though they still factored into media repertoires, discussed below).

Beyond just becoming familiar, some embraced the particularly 'sharp' critique of mainstream media expressed by interlopers. As one participant said, "It's good to have rebellions on the news websites" [p7]. Another added:

What I really like about TYT [The Young Turks] is that they discuss a wide range of topics everyday and I feel more of a connection with the analysts because they aren't mainstream in that they don't hold back with any inappropriate commentary. [P13]

Other participants welcomed the new diversity of voices they could go to for news within the sites they reviewed. This was not a universal response, but it was widely expressed. Still others became invested in examining how these sites positioned their work vis-à-vis journalism (one diary entry from P20, referring to *BoingBoing*, said: "Interesting: only one of the staff members of Boingboing.net calls himself a journalist [link] even though I would classify at least half of their pieces as journalism (they report, state sources, quote, etc.)").

Findings II: News as the meeting up of journalists and their publics

Participants' views on their sites can be further categorized along two lines: the content published and how they engage with it as information (e.g. as deep knowledge, or passing acquaintance); and, the nature of the publics for these sites. These orient our attention to interlopers and their content within a journalist-public relationship.

Findings will be presented along these lines, divided into four quadrants: High Information, with a Clear Public (QI); Low Information, with a Clear Public (QII); Low Information, with an

Unclear/Narrow Public (QIII); High Information, with an Unclear/Narrow Public (QIV) (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Quadrant I

The first category of participant reactions to interlopers is by far the most extensive of those catalogued in the research diaries and sessions. In many instances, participants found outsider content contributed meaningfully to their own daily lives, and further saw a wider public for that content. This included when participants saw themselves as members of the public a specific site was addressing, and saw their content as having a high information value (e.g. *The Slot*, *BuzzFeed News*, *Vice*, and *Sikkom*). One typical entry came in response to *Sikkom*: “when you want to know something about what is happening in Groningen then I would absolutely go there” [P21]. Others found themselves aligning with a public when a site addressed them in a way that was not being done in mainstream news, as P1 said of *Feministing*: “I saw the word community a few times, and it really tries to engage with the readership”. Still others embraced the variety of media forms used by outsiders, including video, cartoons, screen captures, and embedded social media, in ways that were effective and personally gratifying. Referring to a cartoon on *BoingBoing*, “it was really ironic and it was really explanatory [...] it really puts the issue out there and it explains it very easily and very thoroughly, and it also made fun of Jeff Sessions which I personally thought was good” [P9].

While there was some adjustment to the style on these sites, at the same time participants found informative benefits to the alternative approaches taken. As a typical response, one participant wrote about *BuzzFeed News*:

it really contextualized this small remark and showed how much it can mean to a fairly large group of people. And that is something traditional media would most probably glance over, or at least not approach it in this way, even though it does work – it engages the reader into politics. [P20]

To most, interloper content provided a “breath of fresh air” when presenting news they found meaningful for their lives. Participants expressed surprise at stories they hadn’t heard about before, which led them to seek out further information on topics interlopers covered (specifically mentioned were stories on US immigration, on digital privacy rules, and on a Dutch music festival, which were not being covered by traditional media.

Mostly, participants came to terms with subjectivity quickly (they accepted this, though two participants found this aspect of interloper work uncomfortable in the initial days): “of course I want objectivity, but I accept [...] that on *BoingBoing* I found articles in which prime ministers were insulted, so it is like, ‘ok that is not very professional’ but because I am looking for that kind of news, maybe it still has a place” [P5].

In some circumstances participants could identify a clear public for interloper content, though they did not feel they belonged to it. This was mentioned when they were not interested in the specific subject matter (UK politics, *Order-Order* and *Canary* were mentioned) – “I see when you are conservative and working for the government that somehow this might be interesting because you know all the names and you know the abbreviations, you know what is going on and then it might be interesting” [P9] – and when participants felt disconnected from the national context (US news covered by *The Slot*), or found the style of content unappealing (*BoingBoing*). In these instances, participants reflected on their disinterest or dislike as personal but not disqualifying. As one participant said after exploring content from *Vice* in the first research session: “Sometimes it crosses the line for my standard, but still, that journalism is needed” [P7]. For another, after two weeks of reading *Jezebel’s* celebrity coverage: “I do not think that they are relevant, but they should be there” [P4].

This negotiation was a recurring theme, with participants recognizing the value of content with which they did not agree, and recognizing that some media were speaking to different publics to which they did not belong. This was often referenced in comparisons participants drew between different sites they were monitoring. Often, this resulted in reflecting on the content as an ongoing negotiation between subjectivity and balance, and noting that these were also subjective:

Sometimes they make it really bad, like how they are very pushy and being very like, not being relevant to anything. But sometimes they also recognize the other side which makes sense ... it helps us understand the other side as well, so it depends on the person I guess. [P16]

Quadrant II

The second category of responses includes those where participants recognized the importance of the content for an identifiable public, but either due to tone or level of content, found their sites were not in and of themselves informative. This is categorized as high public-recognition, low-knowledge acquisition. In response to this, participants would either disengage or navigate to other sources they trusted, either to expand on journalistic content or to make sense of a story that was minimally discussed or to alleviate doubt (either out of curiosity, or caution):

I think every story on “my” sites is true, but it is just brought up in a very subjective way. In the evening I often watch news on the television, so that is also a way of confirming the news that I read on my sites. [P7]

In this way, content which emerged on interloper sites might only elevate to a type of knowledge when brought together in a constellation of other media content.

In some cases, this constellation was constructed on the sites themselves, as with this comment referring to the way *Geen Stijl* brought a story together via links and screenshots from other media: “they made their own story out of it so I liked that” [P4]. This reflects – in perhaps an alternative way – Nielsen’s (2017) news-as-relations. This is similar to how one participant found *BoingBoing* acted as a sort of “press agency”, as many of its stories “give you the hint [of a story] but not the deeper knowledge about it” [P7]. Participant 7 would then acquaint themselves with a number of news events via *BoingBoing*, and would read more about these in traditional media.

However, participants also navigated away from sites when stories seemed surprising, and any knowledge from them dubious. For instance, during a period of coverage on the US government separating immigrant families, one participant was hesitant to believe stories they came across without first checking elsewhere:

I was immediately skeptical when I saw this because there doesn’t seem to be any proof of its validity. I have been touched by the stories I have read about the incidents at the border in the past week and don’t want to downplay the issue in any way. However, I searched in Google for verification and BuzzFeed seems to be the only news site that discussed this. [P13]

Other participants found themselves building a media repertoire around coverage of news in other countries, suggesting these stories met a news-as-items category, but only when brought into a larger discussion. Referring to stories on the site *Bellingcat*: “I could follow three sources in three different languages and then the English one was actually the best even though it is about Eastern Europe” [P5]. One participant found coverage of transgender rights on their sites (especially *Jezebel*) filled a void in their media diets “because they cover a lot of topics that are not covered in other Dutch media that I read” [P20].

An ‘acquaintance’ with information derived from interlopers’ content also surfaced when participants moved away from the main sites to explore social media accounts of their sites (they were encouraged to do so halfway through the study in a researcher prompt in the interactive diaries). Participants saw interlopers’ social media accounts as means to get

narrowly acquainted with news, only navigating to those stories of greater interest; where low awareness could be turned into greater acknowledge: “you automatically get the headline and some information and then you can read more and click on the link” [P3].

Quadrant III

The third quadrant refers to reactions which suggest low information, and a narrow or non-apparent public. In these reactions, participants were outspoken in their dislike of low-information content which had little or no public interest that they could see. These reactions were rare, and found in responses to content participants saw as geared towards a public that was so narrow as to seem to be only composed of insiders (sometimes on the sites *Order-Order* and *Axios*), or in content which seemed more antagonistic than informative. When this occurred, these were also categorized as having a low/narrow public and further as having little informative value as participants would navigate away from these stories to another of their sites. This reaction came mostly in response to the politically oriented sites *Order-Order*, *The Slot*, and *Canary*, but also celebrity-culture sites (*Jezebel*) and perhaps unsurprisingly to the Dutch site *Geen Stijl* [No Style] which bills itself as “Tendentious, unfounded & unnecessarily offensive”.

Rarely were these cut-and-dried reactions, however. In many cases diaries reflect participants trying to come to terms with content they liked – “philosophically” as one participant said – when it emerges in a language or style approach they disliked. One such reaction came in response to a regular feature on *The Slot* called ‘Barf Bag’, running links to other political news sites. Similar to how P7, quoted above, saw *BoingBoing* as a pseudo-news agency, Participant 1 saw the ‘Barf Bag’ positively for avoiding wasting their time with “all the small articles about nothing, basically they put it all in one big thing with humor and links to other websites.” However, this was not always an effective way for them to gain deeper knowledge:

So that was the good part, but the bad part for me was, while I agreed with many opinions [...] everything is presented as being the *most* important, *most* relevant article in this moment. Lots of emphasis on things, the headlines are all either quotes or they use lots of extra punctuation to attract you and when you click on it, almost nothing is going on. [P1]

These types of reactions also came through when participants read an article, but left feeling they did not gain anything from the content they did engage with. As a typical response to this type of content, P4 described how some of their sites “just made major articles about minor issues [...] it was not really a thing”. Participants also identified outsider sites in terms of a narrow public orientation with no greater informative value when the content seemed to offer little information except for a public which was already aware of the larger story. As one participant commented on *Order-Order*:

I am sending a screenshot of one of the news stories which a) demonstrated the author’s opinion about the event through the obviously sarcastic tone b) it is short, no brief back story, it dives directly into the topic. which was sort of a main “theme” for the site from what I have seen by far. [P5]

Quadrant IV

The final category is Quadrant IV, capturing reactions to content that is seen as in-depth, or information rich, but speaking to a narrow or non-existent public. These were very rare. The nature of most media content allows it to be seen by as appealing to *some* public, and this quadrant has both the fewest reactions in this study and the hardest to categorize. However, we can group in this quadrant reactions to content which seemed disrespectful of the public being assembled. Indeed, reactions which indicate high-knowledge/low-public content often surface when participants pushed themselves to read stories they would not have read outside of a research setting. In those instances, participants were turned off from content which *seemed* to be high information, but did not deliver on what was promised. In the final research session, when asked if they would return to any of their sites, participants observed they would not go back to sites which seemed disconnected from their personal or public lives.

A low recognition of a public (or, put differently, a lack of consideration of one's public) was also found when participants grew weary of a certain language style, particularly if it was unnecessarily aggressive or used sensational punctuation, ("Why use punctuation like this!!!!?????" [P1]). Reactions included an acknowledgement that content had the potential to be informative (discussing a major political leader or prominent public figure, for instance), but the style and approach of the interloper was a turn off, so there was little public appeal:

At the beginning, in certain areas, you get really triggered by it. But then I understood it actually has some potential because I was finding myself googling other stuff that they commented, like they post, write one screenshot or something and then you continue from there. [...] so I found it informative in this sense but yeah, generally pissed me off. [P5]

Further, when content was too subjective (often a feature of interloper sites) this could be a point of distance. One participant commented on this in normative terms, regarding *Feministing*: "even though I find it highly informative, I always keep in the back of my mind that it is kind of opinionated" [P17].

Finally, while a niche focus on a site was repeatedly referred to as a positive (it allowed participants to learn deeply about specific topics, and know where to go to learn more), even for those who *liked* their sites, some of the diversions did not gel. This particularly came through in stories which on the surface address a meaningful subject (indicated in the headline), but seemed to alienate an interested public thereafter. As one participant said:

Why is there an article on astrology and politics? Apparently, Donald Trump is a Gemini, but the author asserts that it's not -only- his zodiac sign that is responsible for his actions

Why did I just read this, and why is this even posted on a news site? [P1].

A critical point can be found in the reactions to language that 'punches' down, and for that reason this quadrant offers an opportunity to consider how interlopers' balance or fail to balance their upstart-nature with a desire by those in the public to not be shouted at or talked down to, and which don't consider the conscientious nature of their public. Participants

accepted the critical nature of interlopers, but saw this as more appropriate in some cases (when pushing back against powerful politicians, states, and corporations), and reacted strongly and negatively when it is directed towards young people, in personal comments on politicians, towards celebrities “for no reason”, and on issues of race or immigration. As one participant said of an article on *Geen Stijl* (a site they at times liked, and at other times disliked): “This article is mocking the picture they found. I feel like they are missing the point” [P14], going on to point out how it seemed to be trying to inflame readers. These sorts of practices serve against the interests of sites trying to gain attention and prominence, as participants reacted to such approaches by navigating to other sites (similar to practices observed in Quadrant II).

Discussion and Conclusion

As journalism scholars have tried to wrap their heads around a changing field of journalism in recent decades, a recognition that there seems to be something of a ‘core’ idea of journalism, and something else along the ‘periphery’ has had particular traction (Deuze & Witschge, 2017; Eldridge, 2018). This binary distinction between the center and the edges of the field have value in the ways they allow us to map the central tendencies which allowed journalism to consolidate as a profession in the twentieth century (Waisbord, 2013), and build on sets of “taken-for-granted assumptions” according to which journalists understood their exclusivity (Lewis, 2012, p. 845). These assumptions are now being openly challenged by digital actors pushing in from the edges of this field, seeking recognition that what they do is journalism. Thus, we have a journalistic core occupied by journalists whose institutions, media formats, and approaches resonate with history, and a periphery where alternative approaches to sharing information, born of a digital age, inject uncertainty into how ‘journalistic’ it all is.

The distinction drawn by such work (including my own) goes further to suggest tension between a core idea of what journalism is (or long has been), and those who would suggest changes to this makeup of the field. This is a useful distinction inasmuch as it explains the reactions towards something unsettling, and useful in distinguishing between the most institutionalized versions of journalism and upstarts still seeking traction. It is less useful when it presupposes that such distinctions hold meaning for audiences, particularly for those adept at navigating a variety of media types. Through research sessions and participants’ interactive research diaries, this study has discussed how news serves as a meeting up space in the relationship between news producers (journalists) and their publics, particularly as members of the public form their assessments of how meaningful interlopers are for their daily lives through their engagement with news content.

This paper also shows what we can learn by allowing members of the public to act as critical definers in the concepts we explore as scholars. We have seen here that when presented with interloper content they would otherwise not encounter, members of the public can adapt and apply interpretive frameworks to bring new, interloping, content into meaningfulness for their daily lives – even when it extends beyond what they are familiar with. However, findings also show people are skilled interrogators of content, they will not simply accept novel approaches to news for the sake of novelty. When pushed beyond what is acceptable or informative, they will seek out different content, and will reject those they see as pushing too fervently on particular topics. The same writing style that interlopers identify as allowing their

work to be independent and honest can also grate against members of the public who still, at times, apply normative expectations to the news they encounter (Eldridge & Steel, 2016).

As part of a larger study interrogating the breadth of the journalistic field and its limits, this paper argues that the contextual relationship assumed by both journalists and audiences has the potential to be a critical definer of what journalism is in a digital age. Nevertheless, it has its clear limitations: All participants lived in one city in the Netherlands during the research, the period of study is constrained to two weeks in 2018, the size of the participant group is relatively small, and so is the pool of sites studied. Future research can pick up from these points to broaden the array of media studied, and iterate similar interactive audience approaches. A cautionary note towards such future research: this study found the qualitative approach and in particular the interactive research diaries fruitful for engaging with the complexities of the questions being explored. They allowed a rich body of data to be compiled, and offered opportunities to explore subtle relationships between participants and content. This is not an approach that is easily scalable, as it can be time and resource intensive. In the researcher's view the richness of this approach should not be quickly dismissed for the sake of breadth.

This paper sits among a number of efforts to move past core/periphery distinctions which otherwise prioritize normative and traditional prescriptions of what journalism is or (perhaps) should be. By accounting for the widening range of actors taking on the journalistic mantle, it argues that focusing our attention on the meeting up spaces where interloping journalists and audiences interact on the ill-defined edges of the field, more nuanced understanding of journalism can be honed. Conceiving this 'meeting up' as a critical relationship which defines journalism in a digital age, it has explored how by engaging with audiences and their interactions with news content, we may better understand journalism as something defined through the ways meaning is made from content. Doing so at the edges of an extant journalistic field allows us new ways to examine the limits to what both journalists and audiences are willing to see as journalism. The challenge for scholars is to at once recognize these media exist, that they speak to and inform publics, and therefore warrant our attention, without simultaneously endorsing all those who purport to be journalistic 'newcomers' when their ambitions push against larger ideals. It is a narrow distinction to navigate, but one best done by contributing more attention to it, rather than less.

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